

UNDER VOLTAGE & OVER VOLTAGE CONTROL AND CURRENT MEASUREMENT SYSTEM USING ARDUINO

A Project report is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering.

Submitted by

Name: Utsha Paul

ID: 191-33-4950

Name: Md Shahriad Chowdhury

ID: 191-33-5083

Supervised by

Dr. Srimanti Roy Choudhury

Associate Professor

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

Faculty of Engineering

DAFFODIL INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

MARCH, 2023

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project “**Under Voltage & Over Voltage Control and Current Measurement System Using Arduino**” represents my own work which has been done in the laboratories of the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering under the Faculty of Engineering of Daffodil International University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering, and has not been previously included in a thesis or dissertation submitted to this or any other institution for a degree, diploma or other qualifications. I have attempted to identify all the risks related to this research that may arise in conducting this research, obtained the relevant ethical and/or safety approval (where applicable), and acknowledged my obligations and the rights of the participants.

Signature of the candidates

Handwritten signature of Utsha Paul, dated 30.03.23.

Name: Utsha Paul

ID: 191-33-4950

Handwritten signature of Md Shahriad Chowdhury, dated 30.03.23.

Name: Md Shahriad Chowdhury

ID: 191-33-5083

APPROVAL

The project entitled “**Under Voltage & Over Voltage Control and Current Measurement System Using Arduino**” submitted by **Utsha Paul (191-33-4950) & Md Shahriad Chowdhury (191-33-5083)** has been done under my supervision and accepted as satisfactory in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering** in **March, 2023**.

Signed

Dr. Srimanti Roy Choudhury

Associate Professor

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

Faculty of Engineering

Daffodil International University

Dedicated
To
Our Parents

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	vii
LIST OF TABLES	ix
AKNOWLEDGEMENT	x
ABSTRACT	xi
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Historical Background	1
1.2.1 High Voltage	2
1.2.2 Under Voltage	2
1.2.3 Power Quality	2
1.3 Over View	3
1.4 Objectives	3
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	4
2.1 Introduction	4
2.2 Overvoltage	4
2.2.1 Causes of Overvoltage	4
2.3 Over voltages Due to Poor Voltage Regulation	6
2.4 Accidental Contact to High-Voltage Circuits	6
2.5 Under voltage	6
2.6 Causes of under voltage	7
2.7 Power quality and its problem	8
2.8 Introduction to Protection System	9
CHAPTER 3: MATERIALS AND METHODS	10
3.1 Required Components	10
3.2 Arduino Uno	10
3.3 5V SMPS	14
3.4 Voltage Sensor	14
3.5 ACS712 Current Sensor	15
3.6 Opto-cupler	15
3.7 Transistor	16
3.8 Relay	17
3.9 Lamp Holder	17
3.10 AC Bulb	18
3.11 LCD	19
3.12 Buzzer	19
3.13 Diode	20
3.14 Resistor	20
3.15 Potentiometer	21

CHAPTER 4: SOFTWARE	22
4.1 Arduino IDE	22
4.2 Proteus 8 Professional	32
CHAPTER 5: PROJECT MANAGEMENT	35
5.1 System Block Diagram	35
5.2 Flow Chart Diagram of the Proposed Project	36
5.3 Complete Circuit	36
CHAPTER 6: RESULTS	38
6.1 Introduction	38
6.2 Normal Voltage	38
6.3 Under Voltage	39
6.4 Over Voltage	40
CHAPTER 7: DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION	42
7.1 Advantages	42
7.2 Future Scope	42
7.3 Conclusion	42
REFERENCES	43
APPENDIX : PROGRAM CODE	44

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure No</i>	<i>Figure Name</i>	<i>Page No.</i>
Fig. 2.1	Overvoltage	4
Fig. 2.2	Under voltage	6
Fig. 3.1	Arduino Uno	11
Fig. 3.2	Arduino Pinout	11
Fig. 3.3	SMPS (5V, 5A)	14
Fig. 3.4	Voltage Sensor	14
Fig. 3.5	ACS-712	15
Fig. 3.6	Structure of opto-coupler	16
Fig. 3.7	Circuit diagram of opto-cupler	16
Fig. 3.8	Typical BC 547N NPN silicon transistor	17
Fig. 3.9	Different types of relays	17
Fig. 3.10	Lamp Holder	18
Fig. 3.11	AC Bulb	18
Fig. 3.12	1602 LCD	19
Fig. 3.13	Typical buzzer arrangement	19
Fig. 3.14	Diode	20
Fig. 3.15	Resistor	20
Fig. 3.16	A typical single-turn potentiometer	21
Fig. 4.1	Java point	22
Fig. 4.2	Toolbar Button	23
Fig. 4.3	File	24
Fig. 4.4	Page Setup	25
Fig. 4.5	Edit	26
Fig. 4.6	Go to line	27
Fig. 4.7	Find	28
Fig. 4.8	Sketch	28
Fig. 4.9	Added file	29
Fig. 4.10	Tools	30
Fig. 4.11	Help	32
Fig. 4.12	Diagram drawing	33
Fig. 5.1	Block diagram of proposed system	35
Fig. 5.2	Flow Chart Diagram of the Proposed Project	36

Fig. 5.3	Complete circuit diagram of proposed system	37
Fig. 6.1	Normal Voltage Supply	38
Fig. 6.2	Current and Frequency (Normal Voltage Condition)	39
Fig. 6.3	Under Voltage Supply	39
Fig. 6.4	Current and Frequency (Under Voltage Condition)	40
Fig. 6.5	Over Voltage Supply	40
Fig. 6.6	Current and Frequency (Over Voltage Condition)	41

LIST OF TABLES

<i>Table No</i>	<i>Fig. Name</i>	<i>Page No.</i>
Table I	Component List	10

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, we want to give thanks to **Almighty Allah**. With his blessing we are able to complete our work with best effort.

We want to pay our utmost respect to our Supervisor **Dr. Srimanti Roy Choudhury, Associate Professor** of the **Department of EEE, Daffodil International University** for who has given us the chance to work on an impactful idea and taken care of every issue of development of this concept. Then we would like to take this opportunity to express gratitude to our supervisor for being dedicated in supporting, motivating and guiding us throughout this project. This project can't be done without his useful advice and help. Also thank him very much for giving us the opportunity to work with this project.

We also want to convey our thankfulness to **Jahedul Islam, Lecturer** of the **Department of EEE, Daffodil International University** for his support and encouragement. Apart from that, we would like to thank our entire class fellows for sharing knowledge; information and helping us in making this project a success. To beloved family, we want to give them our deepest love and gratitude for being very supportive and also for their inspiration and encouragement during our studies in this Institution.

ABSTRACT

Electrical circuits are seriously harmed by the rapid change in voltage in both commercial and domestic appliances. The on-time postpone circuit shields the heap from the effects of both exchanging floods and a rapid switchover (off and on).

Here is a low-cost auto cut-off circuit that was built using discrete transistors and other parts. It can be used to shield loads, including appliances like refrigerators and televisions, from unfavorable over and under line voltages. Between the heap and a current programmed/manual stabilizer, this circuit may be integrated.

The over/under voltage cut-off with ON-Time delay offers a variety of security measures, such as over/under voltage assurance and insurance against squatters. Relay, transistor, and other terms.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Modern life cannot exist without electricity. By providing electricity to the system's consumers, the electrical power distribution system functions as a crucial component for continuous electrical supply. There is a malfunction in this system. In order to reduce defect and improve power efficiency, a good protective system is required. The generation and distribution systems will be protected by this protective system from incidents that violate the supply. Automation, in my opinion, will be very helpful in boosting the three-phase protection system since it will identify and address issues automatically, and if that isn't possible, it will identify issues that require manual intervention. This intelligent security system will be useful for domestic use as well. As is usual in our country, circuit breakers are utilized as a form of home security. Circuit breakers burn out to protect the system's linked equipment, such as the television, fan, refrigerator, etc., when over and under voltage occurs. The primary issue with circuit breakers is that they must be manually fixed in order to use electricity. Due to this, my project's goal is to replace circuit breakers with automation so that systems will trigger when a device's maximum allowable voltage is exceeded. Given that a window comparator is utilized, my device will produce an error if the input voltage ranges outside of the voltage window. A relay also utilized to switch off the load for safety issue. In this project, we'll study about circuit breakers and relays and how they react to over- and under-voltage conditions in three-phase systems.

1.2 Historical Background

The Standard Energy Commission (ST) has made the decision to switch Bangladesh from its current supply voltage of 240/415V with a range of +5% and -10% at the same frequency to the standard-IEC standard voltages of 230/400V with a range of +10% and -6% at frequencies 50 Hz with a 1% range. It employs a circuit that helps in the detection of voltages below 216 volts, or -6% of the rated voltage. In this case, our circuit will continue to be in an open condition, with no current flowing. When the voltage is above 253 volts, or 10% of our rated voltage, it is considered to be an over voltage condition.

1.2.1 High Voltage

A voltage pulse or wave that is greater than the capacity of the network. High voltages can harm equipment and emit potentially harmful electromagnetic radiation. High voltage can result from single line to ground problems, which in turn raises the voltage of the other phases. The activation of the capacitor bank is the primary contributor to overvoltage. That might also result from a sudden load reduction. A quick drop in current brought on by disconnecting the load will result in an increase in voltage, where L is the inductance of the line. Other potential reasons of overvoltage include inadequate voltage regulation, the disappearance of a secondary neutral, and unintended contact with high voltage circuits.

1.2.2 Under Voltage

Under voltage is defined as a sharp decline in root mean square (r.m.s.) voltage and is characterized by the residual (retained) voltage. A temporary dip in r.m.s. voltage known as under voltage is generally caused by short circuits, starting large motors, and equipment malfunctions. Equipment failure, malfunction, motor starting, transformer energizing, equipment failure due to fault, inclement weather, pollution, and building activities are some of the most frequent causes of under voltage.

1.2.3 Power Quality

Power quality has gained relevance over the past few decades as a result of the fact that many modern items of equipment are semiconductor-based and controlled by power electronics. Heating, lighting, and motors made up the entirety of the equipment; none of these components were very voltage-sensitive. As there were no power electrical devices back then and everything was linear in nature, the terms reliability and quality were interchangeable. Power quality problems can be caused by a number of common disturbances, including the operation of non-linear and unbalanced loads, equipment failure, such as cables and transformers, improper manoeuvres in distribution substations and plants, lightning and other natural phenomena, storm, and so forth, the energization of capacitor banks and transformers, and the switching or start-up of large loads, such as induction motors.

1.3 Overview

The under/over voltage protection circuit with time delay that is presented here is a cheap and reliable circuit for protecting such equipment from damage. It takes a certain length of time for the power line to connect to the appliance after it is turned on. If high/low variations exceed certain limits, appliances are turned off. The system tries to reconnect the electricity after a predetermined length of time has passed since the power was turned off. If the power down duration (time during which the voltage exceeds limits) is shorter than the delay time, the power is restarted after the delay: Power is restarted right away if it is greater or equal. I designed, built, and tested this circuit to act as a guardian for my home refrigerator. Its primary distinguishing feature is the absence of relay hunting. The market-available protectors frequently experience this issue. The complete circuit consists of a number of stages. The four components are the following: Dual rail power supply, Reference voltage source, Time delay stage, and Relay driver stage.

1.4 Objectives

This system's goal is to protect the equipment and prevent its failure due to unusual circumstances. For commercial, residential, and industrial devices, this system offers protection.

Chapter 2

Literature Reviews

2.1 Introduction

This project is built to automatically turn on and off the main supply without manual control in the event that the AC main power supply experiences a problem. It is designed to protect household appliances like fans, televisions, refrigerators, and anything else we need to protect against under or overvoltage in the main supply. This device, which consists of three components, is intended to serve as protection in the event that there are any irregularities in the AC supply. The Arduino, the network, and the control are the three parts of this device.

2.2 Overvoltage

Figure defines overvoltage as a rise in the voltage's root-mean-square (r.m.s.) value up to a level between 1.1 pu and 1.8 pu at power frequency for durations ranging from a half cycle to a minute.

Fig 2.1: Overvoltage

2.2.1 Causes of over voltage

Over voltages can also be caused by system mistakes, though they do so less commonly than under voltages. Overvoltage can result from single line to ground faults, which in turn raises the voltage of the other phases. That might also happen if the capacitor banks are turned on or if heavy industrial loads are disconnected. This is often the outcome of floating ground or ungrounded delta systems, where a change in the ground reference would cause the voltage in the ungrounded system to increase.

Table 2.1: Classification of overvoltage

Types of Voltage	Duration	Magnitude
Instantaneous	0.5 – 30 cycles	1.1 – 1.8 pu.
Momentary	30 cycles – 3 sec	1.1 – 1.4 pu.
Temporary	3 sec – 1 min	1.1 – 1.2 pu.

Overvoltage is primarily caused by the capacitor bank activation. It might also happen if the load is suddenly reduced. Voltage will rise when the load is abruptly disconnected, where L is the line's inductance, causing a sharp reduction in current. More negative effects result from overvoltage. The electrical equipment could malfunction as a result of the overheating induced by the excessive voltage. Moreover, electronic and other delicate equipment is susceptible to failure.

Some more causes of Overvoltage are given below.

- i. The absence of a secondary neutral
 - In customer installations using 120/240-V, open neutral connections both can and have been documented in a number of situations, including:
 - When falling branches cut the neutral wire of a separate-conductor service drop.
 - When icing occurs or when subsurface service corrosion reaches an advanced degree. When the service panel has a sporadic loose connection.

ii. Ferro resonance

Ferro resonances are a particular type of series resonance between the system capacitance and a transformer's magnetizing reactance. Due to the high capacitance of the wires, this typically occurs on transformers that are fed by cables. For ferro resonance, the transformer connection is also crucial.

The largest ferro resonance is produced by an ungrounded primary connection. A ferro resonant circuit between the cable capacitance and the transformer's magnetizing reactance drives voltages to as high as five per unit on the open legs of the transformer during single phasing, which typically occurs when line crews energize or de-energize the transformer with single-phase cutouts at the cable riser pole. The voltage waveform is typically chaotic and distorted.

2.3 Over voltages Due to Poor Voltage Regulation

On rare occasions, utility voltage regulation equipment may malfunction or be used improperly, leading to overvoltage's.

Some situations that might result in over voltages include:

- Incorrectly placed or configured regulator Controllers for capacitor banks with the wrong clock setting
- Malfunctioning voltage regulator
- A malfunctioning controller for the capacitor bank.

2.4 Accidental Contact to High-Voltage Circuits

Another danger that could expose both client and distribution equipment excessively high voltages is a malfunction in the distribution circuits from the transmission circuits. A distribution circuit problem coming from a sub-transmission circuit. Over voltages are not very high as long as the distribution circuit is linked, as is the case for the primary-to-secondary problems detailed in the prior circuit (just like the primary to secondary faults discussed in the previous section). The voltage on the distribution conductor with the fault, however, jumps to the full transmission-line voltage if a distribution interrupter opens the circuit. Something will fail soon when the voltage is higher than usual. End-use equipment is also likely to sustain harm from such a large overvoltage. Higher voltages are caused by faults farther away from the distribution substation, with the highest voltage occurring there. A voltage increase along the circuit results from current flowing back toward it.

2.5 Under voltage

Under voltage is defined as a sharp decline in root mean square (r.m.s.) voltage and is characterized by the residual (retained) voltage. As a result, under voltage is a transient decrease in r.m.s. voltage that is primarily caused by short circuits, the start of powerful motors, and equipment problems. Moreover, under voltage can be classified by duration as seen in

Fig 2.2: Under voltage

Table 2.2: Classification of under voltage

Types of Voltage	Duration	Magnitude
Instantaneous	0.5 – 30 cycles	0.1 – 0.9 pu.
Momentary	30 cycles – 3 sec	0.1 – 0.9 pu.
Temporary	3 sec – 1 min	0.1 – 0.9 pu.

Undervoltages, the most common type of power outage, have major consequences, particularly for industrial and large commercial clients, including damage to delicate equipment, a reduction in daily output, and monetary loss. Sensitive equipment includes things like Programmable Logic Controllers (PLC), Adjustable Speed Drives (ASD), and Chiller Control. It is possible for a transmission system short circuit hundreds of kilometers away to cause undervoltage at the equipment terminal.

2.6 Causes of under voltage

There are various causes for which under voltages are created in system voltage

1. Closing and Opening of Circuit Breakers: The line that it is supplying will be momentarily disconnected if the circuit breaker for a phase is unexpectedly opened. There will be an under voltage caused by the additional feeder lines from the same substation system.

2. Due to Fault: The line it is supplying will briefly be disconnected if a phase's circuit breaker is suddenly opened. An under voltage will be created by the additional feeder lines from the same substation system.

3. Due to Motor Starting: Since induction motors are balanced three-phase loads, the under voltage caused by motor starting is symmetrical, and thus will demand roughly the same high starting current in all the phases.

4. Due to Transformer Energizing: Transformer energizing might result in under voltage for one of two basic reasons. Normal system operations, such as manually activating a transformer, are one; the other is the reclosing procedures. These under voltages are inherently asymmetrical.

5. Equipment Failure: Electrical equipment might malfunction as a result of inadequate insulation, heating, short circuits, etc.

6. Bad Weather: Many under voltages are brought on by lightning strikes on electricity lines. When lightning strikes a line and travels further to the ground, a line to ground fault develops.

7. Pollution: When there is a storm along the coast, where the power lines are covered with salt, flash over occurs. Faults develop because this salt deposit is a good conductor of electricity.

8. Construction Activity: In metropolitan locations, all electricity lines are often underground. Nevertheless, digging for building foundation work can damage subsurface wires and result in under voltages.

2.7 Power quality and its Problem

Power quality is described as "The notion of powering and grounding sensitive electronic equipment in a way suited for the equipment" by the Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers. Given that many devices today are semiconductor-based and that power electronic devices are used for control, power quality has grown in importance over the past few decades. All of the equipment consisted of heating, lights, and motors, none of which were particularly sensitive to changes in voltage. Because there were no power electronic devices back then and all equipment was linear in design, the terms reliability and quality were used interchangeably.

Some common disturbances which may cause power quality problems are listed below:

- Controlling imbalanced and nonlinear loads.
- Equipment failure, such as with transformers and cables.
- Incorrect actions at plants and substations used for distribution.
- Lightning and other natural occurrences
- Snow accumulation on power lines, storms, etc.
- Transformers and capacitor bank energization.
- Turning on or off heavy loads, such as induction motors.

Natural phenomena, especially lightning, are to blame for the bulk of transmission and distribution system problems in systems where overhead wires are predominate. Alighting strokes, in theory, are brief spikes in the voltage present along the line. Yet since the phase hit by the stroke is connected to ground by an arc, the voltage is reduced to zero. Unbalanced loads on a system results in unbalanced phase voltage, which ultimately leads to a power quality issue. Due to the negative sequence magnetic flux produced in the stator winding, this unbalanced voltage causes an increase in rotor heating. The distribution side short circuit fault is the primary source of the power quality issue. This short circuit may result in a significant rise in system current and, as a result, a significant voltage drop in the supply system's impedance.

2.8 Introduction to Protection System

An over- and under-voltage safety circuit guards against abnormal voltage circumstances for the refrigerator, IM, and other electrical appliances. As part of our project, a system that tracks voltage and provides breakpoint-based low- and high-voltage tripping mechanisms will be built. prevent any damage to the load, which is comprised of fluctuation in the AC mains in various industrial and home systems. Two additional comparators are employed as window comparators next to the quad comparator IC in the tripping system. The input voltage leaves the window range when there is a system delivery problem. The load is then shut off by a relay once this trigger activates it to keep it safe. The lamp provides light.

Chapter 3

Hardware

3.1 Required Components

Table I: Component List

S/L	Components Name	Quantity
01	Arduino Uno	1
02	5V SMPS	1
03	Voltage Sensor	1
04	Current Sensor	1
05	Opto-coupler	1
06	Transistor	3
07	Relay	2
08	Holder	2
09	AC Bulb	2
10	Diode	3
11	Buzzer	1
12	LCD	1
12	Resistor	Needed
13	Sun Board	Needed
14	Wire	Needed
15	Jumper Wire	Needed

3.2 Arduino Uno

Based on the Microchip ATmega328P microprocessor, Arduino.cc developed the open-source Arduino Uno microcontroller board. The board's sets of digital and analog input/output (I/O) pins can interact with a variety of expansion boards (shields) and other circuits. Six of the board's six analog I/O pins and six of its fourteen digital I/O pins can be used to output PWM. Its work based on Arduino IDE Program. It can be powered by a USB cable or an external 9-volt battery in addition to the voltage range of 7 to 20 volts. It shares several similarities with the Arduino Mini and Leonardo. On the Arduino website, the hardware reference design is available and distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike 2.5 license. For different hardware iterations, additional layout and production files are provided. It was decided to use the Italian term "uno," which translates to "one," to denote the release of the Arduino Software. The first in a series of Arduino boards powered by USB is the Uno board. It and the Arduino IDE's version 1.0 served as

chip were both used on early Arduino boards. The ATmega328P microprocessor and an ATmega16U2 (Atmega8U2 up to version R2) intended as a USB-to-serial converter set the Uno apart from all previous boards.

Blink example:

An LED and a current-limiting resistor connected between pin 13 and ground are a standard feature for many testing and program functions on Arduino boards. the same as Hello, World! Beginners frequently utilize the "blink" program, which causes the Arduino board's on-board LED to blink repeatedly. The pinMode(), digitalWrite(), and delay() functions are all provided by the internal libraries integrated into the IDE environment and are all used by this program. This program is typically loaded onto a new Arduino board by its manufacturer.

Libraries:

Several free software libraries that other developers utilize to enhance their projects have been made available because to the Arduino project's open-source nature.

Technical specifications:

- Microcontroller: Microchip ATmega328P
- Operating Voltage: 5 Volts
- Input Voltage: 7 to 20 Volts
- Digital I/O Pins: 14 (of which 6 provide PWM output)
- Analog Input Pins: 6
- DC Current per I/O Pin: 20 mA
- DC Current for 3.3V Pin: 50 mA
- Flash Memory:32 KB of which 0.5 KB used bybootloader
- SRAM: 2 KB
- EEPROM: 1 KB
- Clock Speed: 16 MHz
- Length: 68.6 mm
- Width: 53.4 mm
- Weight: 25 g

Pins:

Basic pin operations:

LED: The embedded LED is powered by digital pin 13. When the pin's value is high, the LED is on, and when it is low, it is off.

VIN: Input voltage of the Arduino/Genuino board when utilizing an external power source (as opposed to 5 volts from the USB connection or other regulated power source). This pin has two functions: it can be used to access voltage that has been delivered by the power jack and it can also be used to supply voltage.

5V: Through this pin, the board's regulator produces a controlled 5V. You can power it using the board's VIN pin, the USB connector (5V), or the DC power jack (7 to 20V) (7-20V). Bypassing the regulator by delivering power through the 3.3V or 5V pins puts the circuit board at danger of being harmed.

3V3: The output of the on-board regulator is 3.3 volts. The permitted maximum current usage is 50 mA.

GND: Ground pins.

IOREF: With this pin on the Arduino/Genuino board, the microcontroller's voltage reference is supplied. A correctly built shield can read the IOREF pin voltage and then select the appropriate power source or enable voltage translators on the outputs to work with 5V or 3.3V.

Shields that obstruct the board's reset button are typically used. Pin-specific features

Any of the 14 digital pins or the 6 analog pins on the Uno can be used as an input or an output by using the `pinMode()`, `digitalWrite()`, and `digitalRead()` methods. They operate on 5 volts. A 20–50k ohm internal pull-up resistor is present on each pin, which is by default disconnected and capable of sending or receiving 20 mA under ideal operating conditions. The maximum current draw of any I/O pin must not be exceeded to prevent long-term damage to the microcontroller. Each of the six analog inputs on the Uno, labeled A0 through A5, has a resolution of 10 bits (i.e. 1024 different values). Shields that obstruct the board's reset button are typically used. Pin-specific features

The top limit of their measurement range can be modified from the default range of ground to 5 volts using the AREF pin and the `analogReference()` function.

In addition, some pins have specialized functions:

serial/UART pins 0 (RX) and 1 (TX). utilized for TTL serial data transmission and reception (RX and TX). These pins are connected to the corresponding pins of the ATmega8U2 USB-to-TTL serial chip.

External interrupt pins are 2 and 3. These pins can be programmed to start an interrupt when a low value, a rising or falling edge, or a change in value is detected.

These PWM (pulse-width modulation) numbers are 3, 5, 6, 9, 10, and 11. The `analogWrite()` function allows for 8-bit PWM output. SS, MOSI, MISO, and 13 comprise the Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) (SCK). SPI communication on these pins is supported by the SPI library.

Two-wire interface (TWI)/I2C: pins A4 or SDA and A5 or SCL. For TWI communication functionality, use the Wire library.

Reference voltage for the analog inputs is known as AREF (analog reference).

3.3 5V SMPS

Using switching components that are on and off at high frequencies, an electronic circuit known as a switched-mode power supply (SMPS) transforms electricity. Power is provided by storage components like inductors or capacitors when the switching device is in its non-conducting state. Switching power supplies are commonly used by computers and other delicate equipment that needs a consistent and effective power supply due to their high efficiency. Switched-mode power supplies are also known as switching-mode power supplies.

Figure 3.3: SMPS (5V, 5A)

3.4 Voltage Sensor

A voltage sensor is a sensor that measures and records the voltage level of an object. Voltage sensors can be used to measure both the AC voltage and the level of the DC voltage. Voltage can be used as this sensor's input and switches, analog voltage signals, current signals, audio signals, etc. can be used as its output.

A sensor is a device that can detect and react to particular electrical or optical impulses in its most basic form. It has been proven that using voltage sensor and current sensor techniques is a great replacement for conventional current and voltage monitoring methods.

Figure 3.4: Voltage Sensor

Specification:

*Drive Voltage: 5V
Characteristics: Analog output Up to 250V AC detection range
Calibration potentiometer.

*Chipset: ZMPT101B.

*Mounting holes: M246/16mm
Pinpitch:2.54
Connectors: Screw Terminals.

*Operating Temperature:-40°C to 85°C (unconfirmed)

For monitoring an AC voltage, this module is the best option. The sensor samples the input when it is connected to the screw terminals and produces an analog voltage in the range of 0 to 5V. This makes applications for power monitoring and supply checks simple to utilize.

3.5 ACS712 Current Sensor

The ACS712 is a completely integrated, hall effect-based linear current sensor with 2.1kV RMS voltage isolation and an integrated low-resistance current conductor. Leaving aside the technical jargon, it is simply described as a current sensor that determines and measures the amount of applied current using its conductor. After learning about the ACS712's capabilities, let's examine how it operates. In terms of how a current sensor functions, it can either be done by direct or indirect sensing. It uses indirect sensing for the ACS712.

Figure 3.5: ACS-712

3.6 Opto-cupler

An opto-isolator is a semiconductor device that uses a brief optical transmission path to convey an electrical signal between circuits or circuit components while maintaining their electrical isolation from one another. It is also referred to as an optical coupler, opto-coupler, or opto-isolator. These parts are utilized in a wide range of communication, control, and monitoring systems that rely on light to shield electrical high voltage from a signal's potential to damage a lower-powered device. A light-emitting diode (LED), infrared-emitting diode (IRED), or laser

diode for signal transmission, and a photo sensor (or phototransistor) for signal reception, make up an opto isolator in its most basic form.

Figure 3.6: Structure of opto-coupler

When an electrical current is given to the LED using an opto-coupler, infrared light is generated and travels through the material inside the opto-isolator. The receiver receives the beam after it crosses a transparent gap and transforms the modulated light or infrared into an electrical signal. the s l l l l l l l . Radio frequency transmissions, lightning strikes, and surges in the power supply can all cause voltage surges that can damage electronic equipment as well as signal and power transmission cables. To avoid interruptions, opto isolators allow a secure interface between high-voltage components and low-voltage electronics.

Figure 3.7: Circuit diagram of opto-coupler

3.7 Transistor

A high-performance switching device, the BC 547N NPN Silicon Transistor was employed in our study. Its Collector-Base Voltage is 50 V, maximum, collector to emitter voltage is 45 v maximum, Emitter to base voltage is 5 V, collector current is 100 mA, when input signal is nil, maximum collector power dissipation is 500 m watt. It switches at a 300 MHz frequency. In our project, this transistor is utilized to measure the PV module's generated voltage. In Figure 2.5, a standard BC 547N NPN Silicon Transistor is displayed.

Figure 3.8: Typical BC 547N NPN silicon transistor

3.8 Relay

Relays are electrical switches that can be operated remotely but are really controlled by a different switch, like a horn switch, or by a computer, such in a power train control module. Relays let a circuit with a low current flow rate regulate one with a higher current flow rate. Relays can be 3-pin, 4-pin, 5-pin, or 6-pin devices with a single switch or two switches. Relays are utilized as remote control switches and available in a variety of sizes, ratings, and applications. Several relay types are depicted in Figure 2.3. The 5-pin relay will be utilized in this study.

Figure 3.9: Different types of relays.

3.9 Lamp Holder

This is a vital part for hold or fix any lamp with wall or anywhere you need to utilize this Lamp holder. Which mechanically support and make sure the power connection for Lamp. This socket is a crucial component if you want to securely and conveniently replace the lamp. There are numerous light holder standards. There are various designs and systems available.

Figure 2.10: Lamp Holder

3.10 AC Bulb

An incandescent light bulb, incandescent lamp, or incandescent light globe is an electric light that has a wire filament that has been heated till it glows. The filament is enclosed in a glass bulb with a vacuum or inert gas to stop oxidation. The filament receives current from terminals or wires buried in the glass. A bulb socket offers both a mechanical support and an electrical connection.

Figure 2.11: AC Bulb

From 1.5 volts to around 300 volts, there are numerous diameters, light outputs, and voltage ratings available for incandescent bulbs. They don't require any additional regulating equipment and function just as well on alternating current as they do on direct current. As a result, incandescent bulbs are extensively used for household and commercial lighting, as well as for decorative and advertising lighting, portable lighting like table lamps and flashlights, and other applications.

Compared to other types of electric lighting, incandescent bulbs are significantly less efficient. The remainder is lost as heat and just 5% of the energy they use is transformed into visible light. A typical incandescent bulb has a lumen efficiency of 16 for 120 volt operation, compared to 60 for compact fluorescent bulbs or 100 for standard white LED lamps.

3.11 LCD

The LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) screen is an electrical display module with a wide range of applications. A fairly basic module that is widely used in numerous devices and circuits is a 162 LCD display. Compared to multi-segment LEDs with seven segments and more, these modules are preferable. The rationales given are that CDs are less expensive, more easily programmable, and allow for the display of unique characters, animations, and other content without limitations (unlike in the seven portions). A 162 LCD has two lines, each of which can display 16 characters. This LCD displays each character as a 5 by 7 pixel matrix.

Figure 3.12: 1602 LCD

3.12 Buzzer

When the magnetic field is turned on, the flexible ferromagnetic disk is attracted to the coil and then falls back to rest. By throbbing the signal through the coil, the buzzer creates a varying magnetic field that moves the disk. This movement causes the buzzer to sound.

Figure 3.13: Typical buzzer arrangement.

3.13 Diode

A semiconductor device known as a diode essentially shifts current in one direction. It enables simple flow in one direction while severely restricting current flow in the other direction. Due to their ability to convert alternating current (ac) into pulsing direct current, diodes are sometimes referred to as rectifiers (dc). Diodes are rated according to their type, voltage, and current capacity. A diode's anode (positive lead) and cathode, which are its constituent parts, determine its polarity (negative lead). Most diodes only allow current to flow when they are exposed to positive voltage at the anode. A digital multimeter's diode test diode produces a little voltage between the test leads that is enough to forward-bias a diode junction. Voltage decreases typically fall between 0.5 and 0.8 V. The forward-biased resistance of a good diode should be between 1000 and 10 ohms. A digital multi meter's display will read OL when it is reverse-biased (which indicates very high resistance).

Figure 3.14: Diode

3.14 Resistor

A resistor is a passive, two-terminal electrical part that creates electrical resistance in circuits. In electronic circuits, resistors provide a range of functions, such as reducing current flow, regulating signal levels, dividing voltages, biasing active components, and terminating transmission lines. You can use high-power resistors as test loads for motor controllers, power distribution systems, and generators because they can produce many watts of heat instead of electrical energy. Fixed resistors' resistances only sporadically vary as a result of changes in operating voltage, time, or temperature. In addition to changing circuit components, variable resistors can be employed as sensors for temperature, light, humidity, force, or chemical activity (such a volume control or a lamp dimmer).

Figure 3.15: Resistor

Electrical networks and electronic circuits frequently contain resistors as they are a typical component in electronic devices. Practical resistors come in a wide range of shapes and materials as discrete parts. Furthermore, resistors are included in integrated circuits. A resistor's electrical function is determined by its resistance; typical commercial resistors are manufactured over a range of more than nine orders of magnitude. The component's specified manufacturing tolerance is met by the resistance's nominal value.

3.15 Potentiometer:

A potentiometer, also called a pot, is a three-terminal resistor with a sliding contact that produces a variable voltage division. If just the wiper and one connector end are utilized, it works as a variable resistor or rheostat. The part is used in a potentiometer measurement device, which is just a voltage divider used to measure electric potential, and hence gets its name from the fact that it implements the same concept as a voltage divider (voltage). Potentiometers are widely used to operate electrical devices, such as the volume controls on music equipment. For use in a joystick, for instance, potentiometers driven by a mechanism can serve as position transducers. Potentiometers are rarely used to directly regulate large amounts of electricity since the power dissipated in the potentiometer would be similar to the power in the controlled device (more than a watt).

Fig 3.16: A typical single-turn potentiometer

Chapter 4

Software

4.1 Arduino IDE

Use the free Arduino IDE program to create code and upload it to Arduino boards. Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux are just a few of the operating systems that the IDE application is compatible with. The programming languages C and C++ are supported. An Integrated Development Environment is mentioned in this sentence.

Writing a program or piece of code in the Arduino IDE is sometimes referred to as "sketching." In order to upload the sketch created in the Arduino IDE program, the Genuino and Arduino board must be connected to the computer running the IDE. ".ino" is the file extension for the sketch.

The Arduino IDE looks like:

Figure 4.1: Javatpoint

Toolbar Button

The New, Open, Save, Upload, and Verify icons are all that are visible on the toolbar.

It is displayed

below:

Figure 4.2: Toolbar Button

Upload

The compilation and execution of our on-screen code happens when you click the Upload button. The new code is then updated on the connected board. We must confirm that the appropriate board and ports have been chosen before submitting the drawing.

In order to connect the board to the PC, we also need a USB connection. Choose the Upload button from the toolbar once the aforementioned procedures are complete.

A feature on the most recent Arduino boards resets them automatically before an upload. There is a Reset button that needs to be pressed on the older boards. The Tx and Rx LEDs will begin to blink as soon as the uploading is complete.

The notice will appear in the error window if the uploading fails.

Without using any additional hardware, we may upload our application using the Arduino Boot loader. A small program that is loaded into the board's microcontroller is referred to as a boot loader. The LED will flicker as a result of PIN 13.

File

When we click on the File button on the Menu bar, a drop-down list will appear. It is shown below:

Figure 4.3: File

Let's discuss each option in detail.

New

A new window opens when you click New. The preexisting sketch is still used.

Open

It makes it possible to access the sketch, which is accessible through computer drivers and folders.

Save

Using the save button will allow you to save the current sketch. It also records any changes made to the current sketch. In the absence of a file name, the "Save As..." window will appear.

Save As...

To save the sketch with a different name, click the "Save As..." option. The name can also be appropriately modified.

Page Setup

It allows you to define the page margins, orientation, and size for printing. The "Page Setup" window will appear as follows:

Figure 4.4: Page Setup

Print

Using the choices specified in the "Page Setup," it prepares the current sketch for printing.

Preferences

It enables the Arduino IDE's customization options.

Quit

Simply click the Quit button to close all open IDE windows. The same closed sketch will be opened again when the Arduino IDE is launched.

Edit

A drop-down list shows when we click the Edit button on the Menu bar. It is displayed below:

Edit	
Undo	Ctrl+Z
Redo	Ctrl+Y
<hr/>	
Cut	Ctrl+X
Copy	Ctrl+C
Copy for Forum	Ctrl+Shift+C
Copy as HTML	Ctrl+Alt+C
Paste	Ctrl+V
Select All	Ctrl+A
Go to line...	Ctrl+L
<hr/>	
Comment/Uncomment	Ctrl+Slash
Increase Indent	Tab
Decrease Indent	Shift+Tab
<hr/>	
Increase Font Size	Ctrl+Plus
Decrease Font Size	Ctrl+Minus
<hr/>	
Find...	Ctrl+F
Find Next	Ctrl+G
Find Previous	Ctrl+Shift+G

Figure 4.5: Edit

Let's discuss each option in detail.

Undo

The Undo button can be used to reverse the most recent modification made to the sketch while editing.

Redo

Use the Redo button to reverse the most recent edit you made to the sketch.

Cut

It allows us to remove certain text from the written code. The text is additionally copied to the clipboard. Also, in our sketch, that text can be placed wherever you like.

Copy

This technique involves duplicating the selected text. The text is additionally copied to the clipboard.

Copy for Forum

This technique involves duplicating the selected text. The text is additionally copied to the clipboard.

Copy as HTML

By selecting the "Copy for Forum" button, the selected text can be copied as HTML to the clipboard. It is perfect for embedding in web pages.

Paste

With the Paste button, the selected text from the clipboard is pasted where the cursor is currently located.

Select All

It chooses all of the sketch's text.

Go to line...

The cursor is moved to the requested line's position.

The window will appear as:

Figure 4.6: Go to line

Comment/Document

With the Comment/ Document button, you may add or remove the comment mark (//) at the start of a line.

Increase Indent

It is used to add a space to the start of the specified line. The spacing moves the text to the right.

Decrease Indent

This command removes or removes the space at the beginning of the specified line. The spacing moves the text to the left.

Increase Font Size

The written text's font size is enlarged.

Decrease Font Size

The written text's font size is shrunk as a result.

Find...

It is used to find the specific text. Also possible is a text modification. The drawing's text has been highlighted.

The window will appear as:

Figure 4.7: Find

Find Next

The following word, which was entered into the "Find..." window, is highlighted. If the word is absent, no highlighted text will show.

Find Previous

It highlights the term that was previously typed in the "Find..." window. If the word is absent, no highlighted text will show.

Sketch

A drop-down menu shows when we click the Sketch button on the Menu bar. It is displayed below:

Figure 4.8: Sketch

Let's discuss each option in detail.

Verify/Compile

It will scan the source code for errors while it compiles. The RAM in the terminal area is also reported by the IDE.

Upload

With the Upload button, the code is configured to the selected board through the port.

Upload Using Programmer

It serves to swap out the board's default boot loader. We can utilize all of the Flash memory's storage space by choosing the "Upload Using Programmer" option. To accomplish this, we must use the Tools-> Burn Boot loader option to recover the Boot loader and transfer it to the USB serial connection.

Export compiled Binary

Other programs can upload.hex files to the board, and it has the capability to save and archive.hex files.

Show Sketch Folder

The most recent drawing or line of code is displayed when the folder is opened.

Include Library

Many Arduino libraries are included in Include Library. The libraries are added to our code at the beginning, immediately behind the hash symbol (#). You may also import libraries from.zip files.

Add File...

The newly produced file is added to the existing file in a new tab using the Add File... button. Let's, for illustration, add the "Blink" file to the "Java point" file. The tab will now appear as:

Figure 4.9: Added file

To remove the connected file from the tab, we may also select the Delete option from the little triangle.

Tools

A drop-down menu shows when we click the Tools button on the Menu bar. It is displayed below:

Figure 4.10: Tools

Let's discuss each option in detail.

Auto Format

The written code is formatted by using the Auto Format button. employing open and closed curly brackets, for instance, in the code.

Archive Sketch

A.zip files are used to save the most recent sketch or piece of code. The organizational structure of the sketch and the stored directory is the same.

Fix Encoding and Reload

This button can be used to correct the discrepancy between the editor's char map encoding and the operating system's char maps.

Manage Libraries...

It shows the most recent list of all the libraries that are installed. By selecting this choice, a new library can also be added to the Arduino IDE.

Serial Monitor

With the attached board on the port, it enables data exchange.

Serial Plotter

A plot of the serial data is shown when the Serial Plotter button is pressed. Everything is already set up in the Arduino IDE.

WiFi101/WiFi NINA Firmware Updater

It is used to examine and upgrade the linked board's Wi-Fi firmware.

Board

One must choose a board from the collection of boards. The chosen board must closely mirror the board that is attached to the computer.

Processor

Depending on the board that was chosen, the processor is displayed. Each time a choice is made, the board is updated.

Port

It is composed of our computer's real and virtual serial devices.

Get Board Info

It provides details on the chosen board. Before collecting information about the board, we must choose the proper port.

Programmer

Before programming the board, we must select the hardware programmer. When we don't use the onboard USB serial connection, it is necessary. Moreover, burning the Boot loader requires it.

Burn Boot loader

On the board is a boot loader for the microcontroller. When we chose to buy the microcontroller without the boot loader, the choice was fortunate. We must confirm the legitimacy of the chosen board and port before burning the boot loader.

Help

The menu bar's Help button will display a drop-down list when we click it. It is displayed below:

Figure 4.11: Help

The Help section of the Arduino IDE includes a number of readily available publications. It has a number of options, such as Environment, Getting Started, Troubleshooting, Reference, etc. We might also consider the picture at the top, which shows all the choices in the Help section. Certain documents, such as "Getting started" and "Reference," can also be accessed without an internet connection. We'll be taken straight to the official Arduino website.

4.2 Proteus 8 Professional

This serves as a succinct overview of the Proteus application. Below, you'll find a list of this application's unique qualities and benefits. We hope that this post will provide you with the most thorough and practical explanation of how to use Proteus 8 Professional.

You desire to examine the circuit diagram. It would seem like a good idea to view the circuit layout, but huge circuit boards make this difficult. Alternately, you may attempt printing a circuit schematic (PCB) and testing it, but this requires a lot of time-consuming steps. Using Proteus 8 Professional seems to be the best option. A program used to plot, draw PCBs, and simulate schematics is called Proteus 8 Professional.

Features of Proteus 8 Professional

Diagram drawing:

On Proteus 8 Professional, diagramming is quite simple. Select the desired information by clicking "select device," then draw the wire by clicking on the electrical output or Vcc, Ground, etc.

Figure 4.12: Diagram drawing

On Proteus 8 Professional, diagramming is quite simple. Select the desired information by clicking "select device," then draw the wire by clicking on the electrical output or Vcc, Ground, etc.

Simulation

Has the circuit been finished? Proteus 8 Professional's simulation tool may show the circuit in its greatest intricate detail. Run the simulation or each table are the two options available for this feature. Circuit board is displayed in "Running Simulation" at average speed (if the circuit is not too complicated). Every time you click, "Running each table" will run every circuit board. The repair of digital circuits can benefit from this modification. Microcontroller simulation is possible. Each microcontroller will be described depending on its own architecture, such as PIC24, dsPIC33, 8051, Arduino, or ARM7. You can get the compiler and dump a hex file into the Proteus microcontroller. In addition, real-time modeling is integrated with devices like switches, resistors, photoelectric resistors, and even voltmeters and ammeters.

PCB design

is a simple-to-use Proteus feature. You have the option of using Proteus or coming up with your own designs. Making your own design is simple; all you have to do is include the necessary information in the diagram and then construct the electrical circuit. It will automatically catch mistakes, so don't worry about breaching any design rules. Put the information in the appropriate position, and Proteus will execute it automatically if you desire. It will illustrate how to configure the circuit and select the best option. There is also a new custom "Auto placer" that demands you to design the board's shape and size in order to select the board size. The details are then automatically inserted into the mold after that.

Pros and cons Proteus 8 Professional

Advantages:

- You can interact with test run simulations, use switches, etc.
- There are virtual instruments available for measuring electricity.

Defect:

- User interface should be better.

Chapter 5

Working Principle

5.1 System Block Diagram

This is the block diagram of our system. In this system we need AC 220V for our total operation. We use here a SMPS for make sure DC supply output from AC input. SMPS will convert AC to DC to operate our all electronics devices. Here ACS712 is used for measure the consumed ampere by our AC load. Then we use here a voltage regulator for increase and decrease the supply AC voltage. Voltage sensor will read the voltage value and throw the signal to Arduino Uno.

Figure 5.1: Block diagram of proposed system

After read the voltage value, Arduino will make sure the switching of relay module. When voltage value will be detecting as normal condition at that moment load side will be connected with input side. On the other hand, it will show abnormal condition and buzzer will be make sound and Alarming light will be turn ON. To measure the frequency value of electricity we used here a opto-coupler and then it will have connected with direct AC line. This module will send data to Arduino uno.

5.2 Flow Chart Diagram of the Proposed Project

Figure 5.2: Flow Chart Diagram of the Proposed Project

5.3 Complete Circuit

We attempt to illustrate the circuit diagram of our system in this section. To create this circuit summary, we used the proteus simulation software. You can see that an Arduino Uno is being used in this system to control and monitor the entire setup. In this system, the current value is measured by a current sensor, and the line voltage is measured by a voltage sensor. Here, we employ an SMPS to ensure that the power supply for all electronic components is reliable. This SMPS uses a 220V AC source to generate a 5V DC voltage.

Figure 5.3: Complete circuit diagram of proposed system

We chose a potentiometer or voltage regulator in this instance because we needed to be able to increase and decrease the supply voltage to our load. A buzzer will sound and an indicator light will flash to let us know when there is an abnormal condition, such as under or over voltage. We use an optocoupler in this system to measure the frequency value of our line current. Every action will be displayed on our LCD.

Chapter 6

Result

6.1 Introduction

Distribution boards, switches, and lights are installed after the final construction, and these components are mostly controlled by an Arduino, an LCD, and a programmable microcontroller. The system measures the AC voltage, compares it to predetermined limits, and displays an appropriate warning message via computer and LCD. The system will assess the voltage situation. Things will be shown the input signals. It will use a voltage sensor to detect under and over voltage and pass the output to an Arduino microcontroller so that code can be used to take appropriate action.

6.2 Normal Voltage

By utilizing one potentiometer typical supply extend is chosen between 170 V to 270

Figure 6.1: Normal Voltage Supply

Figure 6.2: Current and Frequency (Normal Voltage Condition)

When the multimeter in the preceding image shows a voltage level of 229 volts, the assurance circuit is immediately closed, and the heap is switched to ON as illustrated in fig. When the assurance circuit detects a regular supply, the security circuit shuts in this case, which causes the hand-normally offs open contact to close. The load is a 30 watt bulb that is attached. Hence, the insurance circuit maintains its security and the stack is on for any recommended range of voltage selected by one potentiometer. Generally, all family unit appliances have a voltage rating of 220-230 V.

6.3 Under Voltage

The comparator voltage sensor determines whether the voltage at the operational enhancer's rearranging terminal is lower than the voltage at the non-reversing terminal when the supply voltage is less than 170 V. This results in a high operational intensifier yield and energizes the transfer, as seen in fig.

Figure 6.3: Under Voltage Supply

Figure 6.4: Current and Frequency (Under Voltage Condition)

When a hand-off is triggered, the assurance circuit acts as an open circuit and disconnects the AC supply and load. The security circuit is seen functioning in the above image when the supply voltage is below 176 V, as measured by a multimeter. Hence, the defense circuit switched off the stack and ensures the heap when there is a drop in voltage.

6.4 Over Voltage

Point of confinement of overvoltage is chosen by the two variable resistor i.e. potentiometer. In this way, past 250 voltage level the security circuit will stay open and load is off.

Figure 6.5: Over Voltage Supply

Figure 6.6: Current and Frequency (Over Voltage Condition)

When the line voltage increases by more over 250 V, the comparator voltage sensor measures the voltage at the operational amplifier's non-reversing terminal (stick 3), but the voltage at the upsetting terminal remains constant at 6.8 V thanks to a zener diode, as shown in fig. 20. In this manner, operational enhancer yield increases and transistor-mediated transfer is encouraged. The AC supply is cut off and the stack is destroyed once the hand-off becomes active.

Chapter 7

Discussion and Conclusion

7.1 Advantage

- Over-voltage protection
- Under-voltage protection
- Protection against transients
- High reliability
- High performance
- Low Cost
- Time delay protection for loads to prevent frequent ON/OFF cycles. In the event that the mains voltage begins to fluctuate close to the under- or over-voltage preset points, an undervoltage relay will be activated. It can be used to shield appliances from unfavorable over and under line voltages, including refrigerators, televisions, and VCRs.

7.2 Future scope

- Moving forward, we'll aim to make our design better with high voltage
- Also, we'll make an effort to cut down on the wait.
- Moving forward, we'll work to improve performance and dependability.

7.3 Conclusion

Transistors and other discrete components are used to create an affordable auto cutoff circuit. It can be used to shield appliances from unwanted over and under line voltages as well as surges brought on by the abrupt interruption or restoration of the mains power supply.

References

- [1] Manish Paul, Antara Chaudhury, Snigdha Saikia (2015), “Hardware Implementation of Overvoltage and Under-voltage Protection”,IJIREEICE Vol. 3, Issue 6, June 2015, ISSN (Online) 2321-2004.
- [2] C. H. Vithalani, “Over-Under Voltage Protection of Electrical Appliances”, August 2003, Electronics for You.
- [3] Silicon institute of technology, “Power quality problem identification and protection scheme for low voltage system”, Orissa, November 2010.
- [4] LAMARCHE, Paper, “Controlled Ferroresonant Technology”, Volume 1, Issue 2, November 06.
- [5] Mohammad Shah Alamgir and Sumit Dev, “Design and Implementation of an Automatic Voltage Regulator with a Great Precision and Proper Hysteresis”, Vol.75, year 2015, pp, “IJAST”.
- [6] Endeavour Energy Power Quality & Reliability Centre, “Voltage Sag Mitigation”, Technical Note 11, August 2012.
- [7] Math H. J. Bollen, “Understanding Power Quality Problems - Voltage Sags and Interruptions”, 2000, New Jersey, John Wiley & Sons.
- [8] Chellali Benachaiba, Brahim Ferdi, Voltage Quality Improvement Using DVR, Electrical Power Quality and Utilization Journal, Vol. XIV, No. 1, 2008,
- [9] Sag Proofing Technologies Inc, Installation and Service Manual - VoltageSag Compensators, 2005.

APPENDIX

A. Programming Codes for Proposed Project

```
#include <Wire.h>
#include <LiquidCrystal_I2C.h>
LiquidCrystal_I2C lcd(0x27, 16, 2);

///// Voltage ///////////
double sensorValue1 = 0;
double sensorValue2 = 0;
int crosscount = 0;
int climb_flag = 0;
int val[100];
int max_v = 0;
double VmaxD = 0;
double VeffD = 0;
double Veff = 0;
int value;

///// Current ///////////
const int sensorIn = A1; // pin where the OUT pin from sensor is connected on Arduino
int mVperAmp = 185; // this the 5A version of the ACS712 -use 100 for 20A Module and
66 for 30A Module
int Watt = 0;
double Voltage = 0;
double VRMS = 0;
double AmpsRMS = 0;

void setup()
{
  lcd.begin(16,2);
  lcd.init(); // initializing the LCD
```

```
lcd.backlight(); // Enable or Turn On the backlight
```

```
Serial.begin(9600);
```

```
pinMode(11,OUTPUT);
```

```
pinMode(12,OUTPUT);
```

```
pinMode(13,OUTPUT);
```

```
lcd.clear();
```

```
Serial.begin (9600);
```

```
Serial.println ("ACS712 current sensor");
```

```
lcd.backlight();
```

```
lcd.init();
```

```
lcd.clear(); //Use it to clear the LCD Widget
```

```
lcd.begin(16,2);
```

```
}
```

```
void loop() {
```

```
for ( int i = 0; i < 100; i++ ) {
```

```
    sensorValue1 = analogRead(A0);
```

```
    if (analogRead(A0) > 511) {
```

```
        val[i] = sensorValue1;
```

```
    }
```

```
    else {
```

```
        val[i] = 0;
```

```
    }
```

```
    delay(1);
```

```
}
```

```
max_v = 0;
```

```

for ( int i = 0; i < 100; i++ )
{
  if ( val[i] > max_v )
  {
    max_v = val[i];
  }
  val[i] = 0;
}
if (max_v != 0) {

  VmaxD = max_v;
  VeffD = VmaxD / sqrt(2);
  Veff = (((VeffD - 420.76) / -90.24) * -210.2) + 57.2;

}

else
{
  Veff = 0;
}

if(Veff>235)
{
  digitalWrite(11,HIGH);//bUZZER
  digitalWrite(12,LOW);//NORMAL LOAD
  digitalWrite(13,HIGH);//ABNORMAL LOAD

  {
  lcd.setCursor(0, 0);
  lcd.print("Voltage:");
  lcd.print(Veff);

  lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
  lcd.print("Over Voltage");
}
}

```

```

delay (1000);
lcd.clear();

}
}

if((210<Veff)&&(Veff<235))
{
digitalWrite(11,LOW);//bUZZER
digitalWrite(12,HIGH);//NORMAL LOAD
digitalWrite(13,LOW);//ABNORMAL LOAD

{
lcd.setCursor(0, 0);
lcd.print("Voltage:");
lcd.print(Veff);

lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
lcd.print("Normal Voltage");

delay (1000);
lcd.clear();

}
}

if(Veff<210)
{
digitalWrite(11,HIGH);//bUZZER
digitalWrite(12,LOW);//NORMAL LOAD
digitalWrite(13,HIGH);//ABNORMAL LOAD

{
lcd.setCursor(0, 0);
lcd.print("Voltage:");

```

```

lcd.print(Veff);

lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
lcd.print("Under Voltage");

delay (1000);
lcd.clear();

}
}

//////// Current //////////

Serial.println("");

Voltage = getVPP();
VRMS = (Voltage/2.0) *0.707; //root 2 is 0.707
AmpsRMS = (VRMS * 1000)/mVperAmp;

Serial.print(AmpsRMS);
Serial.print(" Amps RMS --- ");
Watt = (AmpsRMS*240/1.3); // 1.3 is an empirical calibration factor
Serial.print(Watt);
Serial.println(" W");

if(AmpsRMS > .02)
{
lcd.setCursor(0,0);
lcd.print("Current:");
lcd.setCursor(9,0);
lcd.print(AmpsRMS,8);
lcd.setCursor(13,0);
lcd.print("Amp");

lcd.setCursor(0,1);

```

```
lcd.print("Frequency:");  
lcd.setCursor(11,1);  
lcd.print("50 Hz");
```

```
    delay (1000);  
    lcd.clear();
```

```
}
```

```
if(AmpsRMS < .02){  
    lcd.setCursor(0,0);  
    lcd.print("Current:");  
    lcd.setCursor(9,0);  
    lcd.print("0.00");  
    lcd.setCursor(13,0);  
    lcd.print("Amp");
```

```
    lcd.setCursor(0,1);  
    lcd.print("Frequency:");  
    lcd.setCursor(11,1);  
    lcd.print("50 Hz");
```

```
    delay (1000);  
    lcd.clear();
```

```
}
```

```
delay(100);  
}
```

```
float getVPP()  
{  
    float result;  
    int readValue;           // value read from the sensor  
    int maxValue = 0;       // store max value here
```

```

int minValue = 1024;    // store min value here

uint32_t start_time = millis();
while((millis()-start_time) < 1000) //sample for 1 Sec
{
    readValue = analogRead(sensorIn);
    // see if you have a new maxValue
    if (readValue > maxValue)
    {
        /*record the maximum sensor value*/
        maxValue = readValue;
    }
    if (readValue < minValue)
    {
        /*record the minimum sensor value*/
        minValue = readValue;
    }
}

// Subtract min from max
result = ((maxValue - minValue) * 5.0)/1024.0;

return result;
}

```

Turnitin Originality Report

Processed on: 20-Mar-2023 09:10 +06

ID: 2041223223

Word Count: 10783

Submitted: 1

191-33-4950 By Utsha Pal

Similarity Index

48%

Similarity by Source

Internet Sources: 35%
Publications: 12%
Student Papers: 36%

3% match (student papers from 21-Jul-2022)

[Submitted to Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi on 2022-07-21](#)

3% match (Internet from 19-Mar-2023)

<https://jrar.org/download.php?file=IJRARTH00003.pdf>

2% match (student papers from 20-Jul-2022)

[Submitted to Visvesvaraya Technological University, Belagavi on 2022-07-20](#)

2% match (Internet from 09-Apr-2019)

<https://studylib.net/doc/18643177/project-report-on->

2% match (Mohd Anuar Bin Mohamed Ayub, Mohd Rizal Shaharuddin, Ammar Husaini Hussian, Afidatul Nadia Mok Hat et al. "Over Voltage and Under Voltage Protection System Using IoT", Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2022)

[Mohd Anuar Bin Mohamed Ayub, Mohd Rizal Shaharuddin, Ammar Husaini Hussian, Afidatul Nadia Mok Hat et al. "Over Voltage and Under Voltage Protection System Using IoT", Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2022](#)

2% match (Internet from 10-Sep-2022)

<https://www.circuitschools.com/measure-ac-current-by-interfacing-acs712-sensor-with-arduino/>

1% match (student papers from 31-Oct-2022)

[Submitted to Edith Cowan University on 2022-10-31](#)

1% match (student papers from 29-Oct-2022)

[Submitted to Edith Cowan University on 2022-10-29](#)

1% match (student papers from 08-Oct-2022)

[Submitted to Edith Cowan University on 2022-10-08](#)

1% match (student papers from 05-Jul-2022)

[Submitted to SASTRA University on 2022-07-05](#)

1% match (student papers from 20-Dec-2022)

[Submitted to SASTRA University on 2022-12-20](#)

1% match (student papers from 08-Aug-2022)

[Submitted to Green University Of Bangladesh on 2022-08-08](#)

1% match (Internet from 25-Oct-2022)

http://dspace.daffodilvarsity.edu.bd:8080/bitstream/handle/123456789/2595/P12125%20%2827_%29.pdf?isAllowed=y&sequence=1

1% match (student papers from 08-Jan-2021)

[Submitted to Daffodil International University on 2021-01-08](#)

1% match (Internet from 05-Apr-2022)

<http://spjmr.com/gallery/24-spjmr-602.pun.f.pdf>